

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Using the Cell Type Population Predictor

A web application for predicting cell types for tissue samples

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Introduction

Predicting the type of a cell (also called cell annotation, e.g., assigning a cell type linked to Cell Ontology) is a crucial step in single-cell studies and Human Reference Atlas construction. Given a cell type, the functions, pathways, and role of cells in disease and aging can be derived. There exist a number of cell type annotation tools that assign cell types based on gene expression profiles specific for an organ, but they cannot differentiate between more granular spatial locations within an organ. However, location matters. Tissue samples cut from different anatomical structures within an organ can contain very different cell types and biomarker expression profiles, see example for two anatomical structures in heart in **Fig. 1**.

The Cell Type Population Predictor is a no-code application that allows users to enter a spatial origin and get a predicted cell type population (Börner et al. 2025). Predictions made with the Cell Type Population Predictor are at the anatomical structure level, not the organ level (Bueckle et al. 2026).

Computational biologists can use the Cell Type Population Predictor to annotate cell types in single cell transcriptomics based on gene expression markers and in spatial omics data based on protein expression markers. It combines biomarker expression profiles and 3D location data, resulting in enhanced cell type prediction accuracy. The Cell Type Population Predictor can be used to predict cell type populations for datasets for which no assays have been performed yet. After experimental data exists, results can be compared.

The application uses Human Reference Atlas Cell Type Population (HRApop) data computed from high-quality, single-cell datasets processed through scalable, reproducible workflows and cell type annotation tools such as Azimuth (Hao et al. 2021), CellTypist (Domínguez Conde et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2023), and/or popV (Ergen et al. 2024). This SOP assumes basic familiarity with the HRApop effort, see (Bueckle et al. 2026; Börner et al. 2022), as well as with the registration process which is outlined in SOPs including [Using the Standalone Registration User Interface](#), [Using the Embedded Registration User Interface](#), and [Managing Human Reference Atlas Registrations](#). Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**.

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Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Technical Lead** oversees the implementation and maintenance of the Cell Type Population Predictor application and ensures it utilizes the most recent HRApop release.

The **HRApop Lead** guides experimental data acquisition, HRApop computation, and documentation.

The **User** is typically a computational biologist, a clinician scientist, or a bioinformatician who utilizes the Cell Type Population Predictor either with their own data or with the provided sample data.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
HRApop Lead	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
User	various	various

Procedures

Table 2. Deployment URLs, code, and API documentation for Cell Type Population Predictor.

Cell Type Population Predictor	A web application where the user can (1) generate a new extraction site, (2) upload an existing extraction site in JSON-LD, or (3) use an existing extraction site, then receive a cell population prediction based on HRApop data, given the anatomical structure mesh collisions of the extraction site.	Deployed at: apps.humanatlas.io/us1/ On HRA Portal: humanatlas.io/user-story/1 Code: github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-apps/tree/main/applications/us1-spatial-to-cell HRA API endpoints used: apps.humanatlas.io/api#post-/hra-pop/rui-location-cell-summary
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Predicting a cell type population for a known extraction site

An extraction site is a 3D representation of a tissue block, as captured in the Registration User Interface (RUI). Select an extraction site and use the Human Reference Atlas API to predict cell type populations for this site. The demo application at apps.humanatlas.io/us1 predicts a cell type population for a user-provided extraction site, where the cell types and their biomarker

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expression values are not known. A screenshot is shown in **Fig. 1**. The code and API calls used by this demo are documented in **Table 2**.

Click to explore other HRA applications

Use an example extraction site

Upload an existing extraction site from your hard drive

Create a new extraction site in your browser with the RUI (see top right)

Click to explore other HRA applications

Use the RUI to define an extraction site in 3D

Shown here is the male, left kidney

Query result as a table where each row is a cell type, the tool used to assign it, the modality, cell percentage, cell count, cell label, and cell ID

Click to download result as CSV

Tool	Modality	% Of Total	# Count	Cell Name in Cell Ontology (CL)	Cell Type ID in Cell Ontology (CL)
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	7.63	Cycling Mononuclear Phagocyte	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000113
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	10.33	Neutrophil	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000775
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	20.38	Plasmacytoid Dendritic	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0001058
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	78.46	Connecting Tubule Intercalated Type A	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_4030020
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	130.87	Natural Killer T	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000814
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	< 0.01%	130.89	Non-classical monocyte	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000875

Figure 1. Annotated view of the Cell Type Population Predictor.

- Provide a spatial location. The User can do this in one of three ways.
 - Create an extraction site using the [Registration User Interface \(RUI\)](#)
 - Upload an existing spatial location in JSON format, e.g., <https://github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-apps/blob/main/applications/us1-spatial-t-o-cell/registration-data.json>.
 - Use an existing extraction site, e.g., the [sample extraction site](#) from the male, left kidney (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2025b).
- Click the Predict button, and a cell type population based on the extraction site will be returned.
- Behind the scenes, the application sends the extraction site to the HRA Mesh Collision API, retrieves anatomical structure tags and intersection percentages between the user-provided extraction site and the anatomical structures it collides with in 3D space (i.e., how much the total volume of the extraction site overlaps with each anatomical structure that it touches), see (Bueckle et al. 2026). The application then calculates the resulting cell type population based on the cell type population for any colliding anatomical structure for which high-quality single-cell data exists. If the extraction site

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collides with anatomical structures for which cell type population data does not exist, the table is returned empty.

- As a result, the application returns a table with one row per cell type, and with columns for the cell type annotation tool used, the modality, the percentage of that cell type in the total summary, a raw count of the number of cells of that type in the cell type population, a cell label, and a cell ID from Cell Ontology or Provisional Cell Ontology, see **Table 3**. Biomarker expression values are not returned to the user because they are not aggregated by anatomical structure.
- Note that different annotation tools predict different cell types and different percentages for the same cell type. As of HRApop v1.0, cell type annotation tools used include Azimuth, CellTypist, and popV.
- Modalities represented are single-cell transcriptomics and proteomics. For a more detailed discussion, see the section titled “Generalization to spatial data” in the paper titled *Cell Type Populations for 3D Anatomical Structures of the Human Reference Atlas* (Bueckle et al. 2026).
- Percentage is the percentage of that cell type in the total cell type population for the tool.
- The count is the equivalent for the raw count.
- Cell_label is a human-readable name for the cell, typically from Cell Ontology or Provisional Cell Ontology.
- Cell_id is the corresponding ontology ID, using Cell Ontology when available, or Provisional Cell Ontology when necessary.

Table 3. Sample prediction result. This table lists all cell types predicted for the selected extraction site.

tool	modality	percentage	count	cell_label	cell_id
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.149998	260769.8	Cortical Thick Ascending Limb	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_1001109
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.131821	229170.6	Inner Medullary Collecting Duct	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_1000718
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.088839	154445.4	Distal Convoluted Tubule Type 1	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_4030016
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.080101	139255.3	Descending Thin	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_4030012

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				Limb Type 1	
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.076605	133178.1	Connectin g Tubule	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_1000768
azimuth	sc_transcriptomics	0.075927	131997.8	Medullary Thick Ascending Limb	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_1001108

Ensuring accurate cell populations

The HRA Technical Lead and HRApop Lead ensure that:

- This no-code application uses HRApop data from the latest release at <https://purl.humanatlas.io/graph/hra-pop>.
- The data is received via the API calls detailed at <https://humanatlas.io/user-story/1#apis> and <https://humanatlas.io/user-story/2#apis>. They also ensure that these pointers stay up to date even if the HRA API is updated.
- HRApop documentation is updated regularly; HRApop v1.0 is detailed in (Bueckle et al. 2026).
- Document errors by submitting a [GitHub issue](#), or communicate errors to the HRApop Lead or the HRA Technical Lead directly.

References and Resources

Börner, Katy, Philip D. Blood, Jonathan C. Silverstein, et al. 2025. “Human BioMolecular Atlas Program (HuBMAP): 3D Human Reference Atlas Construction and Usage.” *Nature Methods*, March 13, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-024-02563-5>.

Börner, Katy, Andreas Bueckle, Bruce W. Herr, et al. 2022. “Tissue Registration and Exploration User Interfaces in Support of a Human Reference Atlas.” *Communications Biology* 5 (1): 1369. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-03644-x>.

Bueckle, Andreas, Bruce W. Herr, Lu Chen, et al. 2026. “Cell Type Populations for 3D Anatomical Structures of the Human Reference Atlas.” *Scientific Data*, ahead of print, March 19. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-026-06642-4>.

Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center (GitHub). 2025. “Hra-Apps/Applications/Us1-Spatial-to-Cell/Registration-Data.Json at Main · x-Atlas-Consortia/Hra-Apps.” <https://github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-apps/blob/main/applications/us1-spatial-to-cell/registration-data.json>.

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Domínguez Conde, C., C. Xu, L. B. Jarvis, et al. 2022. “Cross-Tissue Immune Cell Analysis Reveals Tissue-Specific Features in Humans.” *Science* 376 (6594): eabl5197. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abl5197>.

Ergen, Can, Galen Xing, Chenling Xu, et al. 2024. “Consensus Prediction of Cell Type Labels in Single-Cell Data with popV.” *Nature Genetics*, ahead of print, November 20. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01993-3>.

Hao, Yuhan, Stephanie Hao, Erica Andersen-Nissen, et al. 2021. “Integrated Analysis of Multimodal Single-Cell Data.” *Cell* 184 (13): 3573-3587.e29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2021.04.048>.

Xu, Chuan, Martin Prete, Simone Webb, et al. 2023. “Automatic Cell-Type Harmonization and Integration across Human Cell Atlas Datasets.” *Cell* 186 (26): 5876-5891.e20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2023.11.026>.

Glossary

application programming interface (API): Software that allows two applications to communicate with each other.

cell type: Mammalian cells are biological units with a defined function that typically have a nucleus and cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane. Each cell type may have broad common functions across organs and specialized functions or morphological or molecular features within each organ or region. Tissue is composed of different (resident and transitory) cell types that are characterized or identified via biomarkers.

cell type annotation (CTann): The process of identifying and labeling distinct cells. Azimuth and other tools are used to assign cell types to cells from sc/snRNA-seq studies. In the Human Reference Atlas, manually compiled crosswalks are used to assign ontology IDs to these cell types.

cell type population: A list of the cell types included in a collection of cell at different scales, such as an anatomical structure, extraction site, or dataset. Currently in the Human Reference Atlas, cell type populations consist of a listing of unique cell types, the number of cells per cell type, and mean biomarker expression values per cell type.

extraction site: Digital, 3D representation of a tissue block. If the Registration User Interface is used to register tissue, then each site has a unique ID; data on size, location, and rotation in 3D in relation to an Human Reference Atlas reference organ; a listing of all anatomical structures that the cuboid intersects with (bounding-box collision by default); and metadata on who registered it.

Human Reference Atlas Cell Type Populations (HRApop): HRApop is a standardized 3D dataset linking high-quality experimental data to Human Reference Atlas digital objects.

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HRApop quantifies the number of cells per cell type within anatomical structures, extraction sites, and datasets while harmonizing cell type annotations using crosswalks to common ontologies. HRApop is published as versioned releases and serves as a healthy reference for researchers aiming to clarify mechanisms underlying cellular interactions as well as cellular and tissue level disease progression.

modality: A specific method, technique, or agent used to analyze a disease or biological condition. Modalities represent the distinct "mode" or "approach" through which researchers or clinicians interact with or observe a biological system. In modern biomedical research, this can refer to different types of data sources used to study diseases. In computational biology the term refers to the output of a specific assay or measurement pipeline, or type of data artifact.

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